

Biological Evaluation of some New Nitrophenoxy/ Halophenoxyacetyl/Propionyl-2-mercaptobenzothiazoles

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In consideration of variety of biological activities of thiazole compounds¹, we report here the preparation and biological properties (anthelmintic, analgesic and antimicrobial) of some nitrophenoxy, chlorophenoxy, bromophenoxyacetyl as well as propionyl-2-mercaptobenzothiazoles.

For a-j : R = H and k-t : R = Me

X	X
a, k 2-NO ₂	f, p 3-Cl
b, l 3-NO ₂	g, q 4-Cl
c, m 4-NO ₂	h, r 2,4-Cl ₂
d, n 2,4,6-(NO ₂) ₃	i, s 2,4,6-Cl ₃
e, o 2-Cl	j, t 2,4,6-Br ₃

The appropriate phenols were condensed with ClCH₂CO₂H and ClCH(CH₃)CO₂H to yield the aryloxy acids (1a-t). The aryloxy acids (1a-t) being refluxed with SOCl₂ yielded the respective acid chlorides (2a-t), which when added to an ice-cold alkaline solution of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole, afforded the final products (3a-t).

Anthelmintic activity : Compounds 3a-t were tested for their anthelmintic activity against the experimental infection of *Ancylostoma ceylanicum* in hamsters and *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis* in rats by the reported method². Mebendazole was used as a standard drug which killed 100% of *A. ceylanicum* at an oral dose of 250 mg/kg × 3 and 70% worms were cleared up in *N. brasiliensis* at a dose of 250 mg/kg × 3. Compounds 3s and 3t eliminated 70–40% worms at a dose of 250 mg/kg × 3 against *A. ceylanicum* and 250 mg/kg × 3 against *N. brasiliensis*.

Analgesic activity : The analgesic activity of the halo series of the compounds at a dose of 100 mg/kg was screened in albino rats of either sex by hot-plate method³.

Compounds 3s and 3t were found to be most active showing PAS 182.38 and 179.75 respectively and their activity was compared with that of the standard acetylsalicylic acid (PAS 204.54) at a dose of 50 mg/kg b.w.

Antimicrobial activity : All the compounds were tested *in vitro* for antibacterial activity⁴ against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus anthracis* and *Proteus vulgaris* and for antifungal activity against *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Candida albicans* by filter paper disc method⁵ using streptomycin and mycostatin as standards. Some of the compounds (25–50 µg ml⁻¹) particularly di- and trihalo derivatives showed marked antimicrobial activity with MIC values ranging from 1 to 5 µg ml⁻¹. Compounds 3h and 3r were found to be active against *S. aureus* and *A. fumigatus* at 2.5–5.0 µg ml⁻¹, while 3i, 3f, 3s and 3t inhibited the growth of *B. anthracis* and *C. albicans* at 1–2.5 µg ml⁻¹.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G plates. Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on an Acculab-10 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian CFT-20 instrument using TMS as internal standard. C, H and N analyses of the compounds were found satisfactory.

Aryloxyacetic/propionic acids (1a-t) : To a mixture of phenol and/or related phenols (0.07–0.1 mol) and 33% aqueous NaOH, was added chloroacetic/propionic acid (0.07–0.1 mol), diluted with a little water to dissolve the salt of phenols and the mixture was heated gently on a water for ~1 h. After cooling, the solution was diluted with water (50 ml) and acidified (HCl) to yield the free acids which were then extracted with ether. The ethereal extract on evaporation yielded the products.

Aryloxyacetyl/propionyl chlorides (2a-t) : To a solution of aryloxy acid (0.05 mol in 50 ml CHCl₃), thionyl chloride (0.06 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for ~6 h on a water-bath. The excess of thionyl chloride was then distilled off under reduced pressure to yield the products.

Aryloxyacetyl/propionyl-2-mercaptobenzothiazoles

(**3a-t**) : To an ice-cold alkaline solution (4N NaOH; 5 ml) of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (0.029 mol in Me₂CO), was added dropwise the aryloxyacetyl chloride (0.029 mol) with constant stirring for about 60 min. The separated nitrophenoxy/halophenoxyacetyl/propionyl-2-mercaptobenzothiazoles were filtered, purified over silica gel column using petroleum ether or benzene or chloroform as eluant and crystallised from benzene or chloroform or ether (yields 52–84%) : **3a**, m.p. 174°; **b**, 181–82°; **c**, 179–80°, δ 2.80 (2H, s, CH₂-C), 6.90–7.40 (8H, m, ArH); **3d**, 210–11°, ν_{\max} 1 240, 655 (C-S-C), 1 240, 1 230, 1 155 (C-O-C), 1 555, 1 345 (nitro group attached to phenyl ring), 1 620 (CO-S), 2 910, 1 485 (CH₂), 3 035, 1 540, 1 455, 1 415, 1 335, 1 190, 1 080, 1 035, 740 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ring); **e**, 161°; **f**, 179°; **g**, 178°, **3h**, 179°; **i**, 183°, ν_{\max} 1 240, 660 (C-S-C), 1 247, 1 230, 1 165 (C-O-C), 1 615 (CO-S), 2908, 1465 (CH₂), 3 030, 1 445, 1 415, 1 182, 1 077, 1 033, 890, 740 cm⁻¹; **j**, 162°; **k**, 170°; ; **l**, 177°; **m**, 173°, δ 1.50 (3H, CH₃), 3.20 (1H, CH), 7.00–7.50 (8H, m, ArH); **n**, 202°; **o**, 166°; **p**, 178°; **q**, 174°; **r**, 177°; **s**, 181°; **t**, 158°, ν_{\max} 1 240, 652, 1 244, 1 235, 1 160, 1 620, 2 900, 1 400, 3 026, 1 445, 1 410, 1 185, 1 080, 1 035, 890, 740 cm⁻¹.

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References

1. B. L. FERBULANDER and F. A. FRENCII, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Bio. Med.*, 1947, **66**, 362; B. JACQUES, A. A. CATHERINE, C. JAMINE, R. CLAUDE, C. GILBERT and B. CLAUDE, *Eru. J. Med. Chem. Chim. Ther.*, 1985, **20**, 43; L. CARP and A. TOMA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, **63**, 1484; N. HANS, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **88**, 22886; T. YAMANKA, K. IKEDA and K. OSUGA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **89**, 24289; J. ZAWAOZAKA, S. SZCZYCINSKI, B. PRAZEMIK and M. BOGUAL, *Acta. Pol. Pharm.*, 1979, **36**, 433 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, **93**, 46496).
2. J. S. STEWARD, *Parasitology*, 1955, **45**, 225.
3. N. B. EDDY and D. LIMBACH, *J. Pharm. Exptl. Thera.*, 1953, **107**, 385; G. CURZON, P. H. HUTSON and M. D. TRICKLEMBANP, *Br. J. Pharmacol.*, 1980, **70**, 44.
4. A. W. BAYER, W. M. M. KIRBY, J. C. SHERRIES and M. TURK, *Am. J. Clin. Pathol.*, 1966, **45**, 493.
5. J. G. VINCENT and H. W. VINCENT, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1955, **55**, 112.